

SURVEILLANCE CARD_Disease Y_Detection of new infectious agent causing disease in Exotic Animals (imported animals e.g., through pet shops or in zoos)

	Characteristics	Description
1	Surveillance component name	Detection of new infectious agent causing disease (Disease Y) in exotic animals
2	Surveillance aim	Early detection of new, disease-causing pathogens in exotic animals
3	Target species and group	All exotic animal species
4	Target sector / production type	Not applicable
5	Geographical area covered	Whole country
6	Age group	Not applicable
7	Sampling point and strategy	Veterinary practices, universities, zoos, etc.
8	Sampling time period	Year-round / not limited
9	Sampling matrix	To be defined based on pathological findings
10	Type of disease indicators	Morbidity and mortality of exotic animal species
11	Sampling unit	Individual animal
12	Allocation of animal groups /animals to sampling	No risk factors
13	Testing protocol / Diagnostic test	Following exclusion of known pathogens, additional diagnostic investigations using metagenomics, whole genome sequencing, etc.
14	Design prevalence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable

15	Level of confidence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable
16	Contribution of the component to the surveillance system	Not applicable
17	Other pathogens that could be targeted with this surveillance component	All other pathogens of exotic animals that cause severe morbidity and mortality
18	References	Not applicable
19	Additional comments	Note: It is important to assure a timely exchange and investigations of similar cases in other animal species and humans